

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Ni^{II} COMPLEXES*Temp.=30°, Ionic strength=0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand (HL)	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	pK_3^H	$\log K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$	$\log K_{Ni.(bipy).L}^{Ni.(bipy)}$	$\log K_{Ni.(hist.).L}^{Ni.(hist.)}$
Glycollic acid	10.53	3.48	—	4.76	5.09	3.53
Lactic acid	10.90	3.53	—	5.01	5.12	4.07
Malic acid	11.90	4.64	3.05	5.50	5.22	4.57
Glycine	9.60	2.31	—	5.90	5.50	4.89
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	—	5.54	5.14	4.64
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	—	7.12	6.72	4.78

*Limits of error in the constants = $\pm 0.02 \sim 0.04$.

solution using a Elico LI-10 T pH-meter at 30°. Representative pH-titration plots in case of Ni(histidine)(glycine) system are presented in Fig. 1. The formation constants were calculated by the literature methods⁴. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$ values are in the order, glycine \approx α -alanine $<$ aspartic acid for the amino acids, and glycollic \approx lactic $<$ malic acid for the corresponding hydroxy acids⁵. The $K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A}$ values are higher than $K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$ for A=2,2'-bipyridyl, and significantly lower for A=histidine.

The higher values of $K_{Ni.(bipy).L}^{Ni.(bipy.)}$ than $K_{Ni.(hist.).L}^{Ni.(hist.)}$ arise due to electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand histidine and secondary ligands. Histidine is anionic while 2,2'-bipyridyl is neutral in the NiAL complexes.

The higher stability of the Ni^{II} complexes with amino acid than the corresponding complexes with hydroxy acid complexes arise from the greater tendency of Ni^{II} to bind with a nitrogen ligand as compared to oxygen.

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Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Benzoic Acid Hydrazones

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IN view of the current interest in the biological activity¹ and structures of hydrazides and hydrazones, a systematic study of *p*-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (abbreviated as HBBH and HMBBH, respectively) have been undertaken. Their complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been isolated and characterised by physicochemical methods.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Commercial ethanol was used after purification by distillation.

p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (HBBH): Ethanolic solutions of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.05 mol, 6.10 g) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.05 mol, 6.80 g) were refluxed for 3 h. The resulting white powdery solid separated on cooling the mixture to room temperature, was filtered, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and finally dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure, HBBH (80%), m.p. 215°, was soluble in hot ethanol.

4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (HMBBH): It was obtained from 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.05 mol, 7.60 g)

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF HBBH AND HMBBH METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			M	O	H	N
HL(HBBH)	White	215	—	69.82 (70.00)	4.87 (5.00)	11.50 (11.67)
CoL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Green	280	10.60 (10.58)	60.12 (60.32)	4.76 (4.66)	9.98 (10.05)
NiL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Orange	300	10.52 (10.54)	60.05 (60.35)	4.82 (4.67)	9.98 (10.05)
CuL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Grey	250	11.39 (11.41)	60.05 (60.35)	4.82 (4.63)	9.97 (9.82)
HL'(HMBBH)	White	180	—	66.45 (66.67)	5.01 (5.19)	10.22 (10.37)
CoL' ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Yellow	260	9.52 (9.55)	58.09 (58.35)	5.02 (4.85)	9.00 (9.08)
NiL' ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Orange	300	9.49 (9.51)	58.12 (58.37)	5.01 (4.86)	9.00 (9.08)
CuL' ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Brown	240	10.21 (10.22)	57.73 (57.92)	5.01 (4.82)	9.00 (8.92)

and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.05 mol, 6.10 g) following the above procedure; HMBBH (85%), m.p. 180°, was soluble in hot ethanol.

The purity of both the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography.

Metal complexes: Solution of metal acetates (0.002 mol) in water (50 cm³) and ethanol (50%, v/v) were mixed with solution of HBBH or HMBBH (0.004 mol) in hot ethanol (100 cm³) and refluxed for 2–3 h. The separated coloured complexes were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried. The complexes were insoluble in acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and ether.

Elemental analysis data are presented in Table 1.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm⁻¹. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded by a VSU-21 spectrophotometer in the range 200–1 000 nm. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done with a Gouy balance at room temperature (25°). TG data were obtained from an assembly capable of producing temperature upto 800° with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes correspond to ML₂·2H₂O stoichiometry, where HL = C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₂ or C₁₄H₁₄N₂O₃; M(II) = Co, Ni and Cu.

Infrared spectra: Free ligands showed the following bands^{3,9} ν_{max} 3 240 and 3 105 (NH), 1 720 (C=O), 3 470 (OH), 1 680 (C=N) and 1 530 cm⁻¹ (C–O phenol). A composite band due to C–NH stretch and N–H deformation appeared at 1 570 cm⁻¹, which suggests that the ligand exists in keto form (I) in solid state. In all the complexes ν_{NH}, ν_{C=O}, ν_{C–NH} and δ_{NH} disappeared and a new band appeared at 1 585 ± 5 cm⁻¹, which was assigned to >C=N–N=C< stretching vibration. This new

band is a diagnostic of the presence of enol forms of the hydrazone ligand in the complexes. Another new band occurred at 1 295 cm⁻¹ (C–O) owing to tautomerism which further supports enol form of the ligands in the complexes. Appearance of a band at 1 645–1 640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is attributed to C=N vibration⁴ arising from

tautomerism confirms the enol form(II) of the ligand (I).

The 3 600–3 690, 1 625–1 620 and 975–970 cm⁻¹ bands in the complexes correspond to stretching, bending and rocking mode of coordinated water^{5,6}. Two C=N stretching frequencies at 1 680 and 1 645 cm⁻¹ arise due to coordinated and non-coordinated cyano group, respectively⁸. The band at ~1 645 cm⁻¹ is a composite band of ν_{O–C=N} + ν_{C=N}. The C=N stretch at 1 680 cm⁻¹ in the ligand showed a negative shift of 40–30 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen on complexation^{7,8}. The 520–510 and 470–465 cm⁻¹ bands in the complexes correspond to ν_{M–O} and ν_{M–N} respectively^{9,10}. The ir spectra of the complexes derived from HBBH are similar.

Diffuse reflectance spectra: The Co^{II} complexes showed two d–d transition bands (ν₁, ν₂) at 10 420, 21 650, and 10 360, 21 510 cm⁻¹ in the HBBH and HMBBH complexes, respectively. The ν₂ transition was not observed¹¹; it was calculated to be 22 716 and 22 292 cm⁻¹ for the HBBH and HMBBH complexes, respectively. The observed magnetic moments for Co^{II}–HBBH and Co^{II}–HMBBH complexes are 4.88 and 4.96 B.M., respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry for these complexes¹².

The Ni^{II} complexes exhibited three bands at 10 420, 16 950 and 24 390 cm⁻¹ for HBBH and at 10 310, 16 670 and 23 810 cm⁻¹ for HMBBH complexes, respectively. Spectral data of the Ni^{II} complexes with HBBH and HMBBH and observed moments of 2.94 and 2.96 B.M., respectively, conform the octahedral configuration with two unpaired electrons. The values of 10 Dq, B', β and nephelauxetic ratio β° have been calculated for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and the values are found to lie in the same order, i.e. 10 420 cm⁻¹, 932 cm⁻¹, 0.882, 11.8, and 11 930 cm⁻¹, 847 cm⁻¹, 0.872 and 12.8 for the HBBH and HMBBH complexes, respectively. The ν₂/ν₁ ratio for the HBBH and HMBBH complexes fall in the range 2.15–2.18 (Co complex) and 1.61–1.62 (Ni complex) which is characteristic of octahedral geometry¹⁸.

The Cu–HBBH complex showed weak band at 10 870, 14 080 and 15 630 cm⁻¹ and the Cu–HMBBH complex showed bands at 11 110, 14 490 and 16 130 cm⁻¹. The ratio σ₁/σ₂ for the above two complexes is 1.22 and 1.36, respectively, indicating distorted octahedral geometry. Magnetic moment values of the Cu^{II} complexes are 1.94 and 1.96 B.M., respectively.

All the complexes formed by HBBH and HMBBH start losing water at 100° and the hydration is complete at 300°. The loss in weight corresponds to the elimination of two molecules of water.

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Interaction of Divalent Metal Ions with Uracil. Part-II. Uracil Complexes of Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II)

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URACIL, a constituent of RNA, exists in the dilactum form both in the solid state and in neutral aqueous solution but has been infrequently used in complexation. Uracil in its neutral form coordinates to the metal ions^{1,2} through the oxygen, but under basic condition in its anionic form it may coordinate to the metal ion both through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. The preparation and characterisation of oxygen coordinated uracil complexes of divalent metal ions have been reported³. In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of some new complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with uracil in its anionic form coordinating through its nitrogen.

Uracil

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of complexes. General method: Calculated amount of uracil dissolved in methanol was added to the methanolic solutions of the respective metal chloride (except in case of iron, FeSO₄·7H₂O was used); the ratio of metal–uracil being 1 : 2 and pH maintained around 10 by adding dilute NaOH solution. The mixtures were refluxed for 10 h when respective crystals separated out. It was separated by filtration and washed with methanol. Thermogravimetric were recorded with a Derivatograph (System : F. Paulik, J. Paulik, L. Erdey, MOM, Budapest). The electronic spectra of the solid complexes were recorded with a Carl Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer and the ir spectra (KBr) with a Perkin–Elmer 257 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are coloured, insoluble in water but soluble in non-polar solvents like CCl₄, indicating their non-electrolytic behaviour. Analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the formula ML₂(H₂O)₄, where M=Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II};